

ON THE SMARANCHE FUNCTION AND ITS HYBRID MEAN VALUE

Yao Weili

Research Center for Basic Science, Xi'an Jiaotong University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, P.R.China

Abstract For any positive integer n , let $S(n)$ denotes the Smarandache function, then $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest $m \in N^+$ with $n|m!$. In this paper, we study the asymptotic property of a hybrid mean value of the Smarandache function and the Mangoldt function, and give an interesting hybrid mean value formula for it.

Keywords: the Smarandache function; the Mangoldt function; Mean value.

§1. Introduction

For any positive integer n , let $S(n)$ denotes the Smarandache function, then $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest $m \in N^+$ with $n|m!$. From the definition of $S(n)$, one can easily deduce that if $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}$ is the prime power factorization of n , then

$$S(n) = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} S(p_i^{\alpha_i}).$$

About the arithmetical properties of $S(n)$, many people had studied it before (see reference [2]). In this paper, we study the asymptotic property of a hybrid mean value of the Smarandache function and the Mangoldt function, and give an interesting hybrid mean value formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \wedge(n) S(n) = \frac{x^2}{4} + O\left(\frac{x^2 \log \log x}{\log x}\right),$$

where $\wedge(n)$ is the Mangoldt function defined by

$$\wedge(n) = \begin{cases} \log p, & \text{if } n = p^\alpha (\alpha \geq 1); \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem. Firstly, we need following:

Lemma. For any prime p and any positive integer α , we have

$$S(p^\alpha) = (p-1)\alpha + O\left(\frac{p \log \alpha}{\log p}\right).$$

Proof. From Theorem 1.4 of reference [3], we can obtain the estimate.

Now we use the above Lemma to complete the proof of the theorem. From the definition of $\wedge(n)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n \leq x} \wedge(n) S(n) \\ &= \sum_{p^\alpha \leq x} S(p^\alpha) \log p \\ &= \sum_{p \leq x} \sum_{\substack{\alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p} \\ \alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p}}} \log p \left((p-1)\alpha + O\left(\frac{p \log \alpha}{\log p}\right) \right) \\ &= \sum_{p \leq x} (p-1) \log p \sum_{\substack{\alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p} \\ \alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p}}} \alpha + O\left(\sum_{p \leq x} p \sum_{\substack{\alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p} \\ \alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p}}} \log \alpha \right). \end{aligned}$$

Applying Euler's summation formula, we can get

$$\sum_{\substack{\alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p} \\ \alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p}}} \alpha = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\log^2 x}{\log^2 p} + O\left(\frac{\log x}{\log p}\right),$$

and

$$\sum_{\alpha \leq \frac{\log x}{\log p}} \log \alpha = \frac{\log x}{\log p} \log \frac{\log x}{\log p} - \frac{\log x}{\log p} + O\left(\log \frac{\log x}{\log p}\right).$$

Therefore we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \wedge(n) S(n) = \frac{1}{2} \log^2 x \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{p}{\log p} + O\left(\log x \log \log x \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{p}{\log p}\right). \quad (1)$$

If $x > 0$ let $\pi(x)$ denote the number of primes not exceeding x , and let

$$a(n) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n \text{ is a prime;} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

then $\pi(x) = \sum_{p \leq x} a(n)$. Note the asymptotic formula

$$\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\log x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\log^2 x}\right),$$

and from Abel's identity, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{p}{\log p} \\
 = & \sum_{n \leq x} a(n) \frac{n}{\log n} \\
 = & \pi(x) \frac{x}{\log x} - \pi(2) \frac{2}{\log 2} - \int_2^x \pi(t) d\left(\frac{t}{\log t}\right) \\
 = & \frac{x}{\log x} \left(\frac{x}{\log x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\log^2 x}\right)\right) - \int_2^x \left(\frac{t}{\log t} + O\left(\frac{t}{\log^2 t}\right)\right) d\left(\frac{t}{\log t}\right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \frac{x^2}{\log^2 x} + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\log^3 x}\right). \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Combining (1) and (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{n \leq x} \wedge(n) S(n) \\
 = & \frac{1}{4} x^2 + O\left(\frac{x^2}{\log x}\right) + O\left(\log x \log \log x \frac{x^2}{\log^2 x}\right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{4} x^2 + O\left(\frac{x^2 \log \log x}{\log x}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

References

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